

A Discourse on Gender Disparity: A Study on Taluks Of Belagavi District

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ABSTRACT

The modern period witnessed the increased gender disparity reflected in sex-ratio, literacy and education, employment and wage-rates and several other socio-cultural and behavioral indicators of empowerment.(Nangia, 2005)Gender equality is more than a goal in itself. It is a precondition for meeting the challenges of reducing poverty, promoting sustainable development and building good governance -Kofi Annan(Personal, Archive, Mahanta, & Nayak, 2013).The present paper examines the extent of gender disparity in Belagavi District based on literacy and sex ratio using secondary data. We found that literacy rate in study area was 76.93 % in 2001 which is increased to 82.90 % in 2011 and sex ratio in the study area was 960 in 2001 which is increased to 973 in 2011. There are wide disparities from Rural to Urban sex ratio as well as Rural to Urban literacy rate. The urban sex ratio is higher than rural sex ratio in study area. The Rural sex ratio is 970 and urban sex ratio is 979 females per thousand males in the 2011. We found that in Belagavi district, there is reduction in gender disparities from 2001 to 2011 but the reduction rate is very slow.

Keywords: Gender, Sex ratio, Literacy, Disparity, Rural, Urban

I. INTRODUCTION

Belagavi district is located in the north-western part of the Karnataka state (Fig. 1), nestling high in the

Western Ghats. It extends over an area of 13,379 Sq. Km which is 6.99 percent of the total geographical area of the state. The district is between 400-900 m above mean sea level. It measures about 160 Km from north to south and 80-130 Km from east to west. The total population of Belagavi district is 47, 79,661 it is almost equal to Singapore population. (Office of the Registrar General and Census Commissioner, India, 2011).The Average literacy rate of Belagavi district (73.48%) is lower than the average literacy rate of Karnataka state literacy rate (75.60%)(“Primary Census Abstract Total Table For India,” n.d.). The average sex ratio of Belagavi district is 973females per 1000 males is almost equal to the sex ratio of Karnataka state (973).Current study focused on taluk wise gender disparities in literacy and sex ratio of Belagavi district and study attempts to analyze taluk wise gender disparities in literacy and sex ratio of Belagavi District.

II. OBJECTIVES

The main aim of this study is to analyze taluk wise gender disparities in literacy and sex ratio of Belagavi during 2001 to 2011.

III. STUDY AREA

The study area of this paper is a part of Karnataka. The region under study extends from 15°–23’ north to 16°–58’ north latitudes and 74°–05’ east to 75°–28’

east longitudes . The Belagavi district is divided in to 10 taluks for administrative purposes viz., Athani, Belgaum, Chikodi, Gokak, Hukeri, Khanapur, Parasgad (Saundatii), Ramdurg, Raybag and Sampgaon (Bailhongal). Belgavi district is bordered by Maharashtra state to in the North, Bagalkot district in the East, Dharwad & and Uttar Kannada districts in the South, Goa and Maharashtra state in the west.(Mr. Arun Nivrutti Chandore, n.d.)Belgaum with a total population of 47, 79,661 is the second most populous district in the State and the district ranks first in terms of rural population and third in terms of urban population. The district with a sex ratio of 973 holds 21st rank in the state, the same rank as in 2001 Census. The district has a literacy rate of 73.5 percent and is placed at 16th rank in the state and the male literacy rate in the district is 82.2 percent and the female literacy rate is 64.6 percent. The male – female literacy gap in the district is 17.6 percentage points, which is higher than themale – female literacy gap registered by the state (14.4 percentage points).(Census of India 2011Karnataka, 2011)

LOCATION MAP OF BELAGAVI DISTRICT IN INDIA/KARNATAKA

Figure 1.

IV. DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY

The present research work is based on secondary data obtained from district census handbook of Belagavi

district, statistical abstracts of Belagavi and Karnataka state and census of India 2001 and 2011. Other various sources of secondary data have been utilized such as internet and books etc. Literacy rate has been computed for the population above 6 years. For the measurement of male female disparity in literacy, the Sopher's Disparity Index (1974) modified by Kundu and Rao (1983) has been employed. Moreover simple mathematical techniques are used to calculate the percentages for sex ratio.The methodology comprises the preparation of Bar graphs for a more effective representation of the data.

Literacy rate is computed for the population above six years of age.

$$1) \text{Literacy Rate} = \frac{\text{Literate population}}{\text{Total population above 6 age}} \times 100$$

2) **David Sopher's Disparity Index:** It is concerned with male and female gap in literacy. David Sopher's index modified by Prof. Amitabh Kundu, and Rao in 1983(Hajare& Ghurake, 2014).

FORMULA

$$DMS = \log \frac{X2}{X1} + \log \frac{200 - X1}{200 - X2} + \dots$$

Where,

X2 is more than X1. X2= is considered Male. X1=is considered Female

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

V. DISPARITY IN LITERACY OF BELAGAVI DISTRICT

Belgavi district literacy rate in 2011 is 73.48% where as in 2001 it is 61.4%,. The male–female disparity was 0.235 in 2001, while 0.165 in 2011. Table 1show that the literacy rate in the study area varied from a minimum of 66.36% in Ramdurg taluk to a maximum of 83.68% in Belagavi taluk of Belagavi district. In the study area the male literacy is 82.2% and for female it is 64.58% in 2011. It shows a wide gap of 17.62% literacy from male to female.

Table 1 Disparity of Literacy, 2001-2011

SL No	Name of Taluks	Literacy-2001		Disparity Of Literacy	Literacy-2011		Disparity in M/F Literacy
		Male	Female		Male	Female	
1.	Athani	72.54	49.00	0.243	79.06	61.47	0.171
2.	Bailhongal	75.44	50.99	0.247	81.8	63.87	0.168
3.	Belgavi	86.46	69.71	0.153	89.63	77.54	0.108
4.	Chikkodi	81.56	56.63	0.241	84.89	67.00	0.165
5.	Gokak	68.70	42.84	0.283	77.75	57.31	0.199
6.	Hukkeri	74.69	49.15	0.262	81.21	62.08	0.181
7.	Khanapur	78.06	53.83	0.240	84.69	66.39	0.169
8.	Raibag	66.62	44.14	0.246	75.53	58.2	0.169
9.	Ramdurg	69.42	40.36	0.322	77.53	54.94	0.223
10.	Savadatti	70.47	42.21	0.308	79.33	57.69	0.209
Belagavi district total		75.70	52.30	0.235	82.2	64.58	0.165

Data sources: Calculated by using data taken from the 2001 and 2011 Population Censuses.

Chart 1: Disparity of male and Female Literacy in Belagavi District

Data sources: calculated by using data taken from the population censuses

Table 1 observed that minimum male literacy was in Raibag taluk 75.53% and maximum in Belgavi taluk 89.63% in Belagavi district. There was observed that the minimum female literacy was 54.94% in Ramdurg taluk to a maximum of 77.54% in Belgavi taluk. It shows that there are wide disparities from the male–female literacy rates.

As compared to 2001, disparity of literacy decreased by 0.07 % in 2011, because of increased literacy rate. Highest disparity of male and female is observed in Ramdurg Taluk (0.223) followed by Savadatti taluk

(0.209), because of wide gap from male to female literacy. Lower disparity of literacy in male and female observed in Belgavi taluk (0.108), because, Belgavi taluk of Belagavi district experiences high literacy rate of both in male and female.

VI. DISPARITY IN SEX RATIO OF BELAGAVIDISTRICT

Sex ratio is one of the important demographic factors that indicate the status of women in a particular society. A social system with higher sex ratio itself

shows the higher status of women (Melorose, Perroy, & Careas, 2015).

Table no 2 shows that, in Belagavidistrict the maximum sex ratio are highest in Hukkeri taluk (991) and lowest in Athani (958) and Raibag taluk (958) respectively. The sex ratio of the district in 2011 is 973 females per thousand males are almost equal to the sex ratio of Karnataka state (973). Sex ratios of the taluks are presented in table -2 and it is clear from the table that there is also continuously increase in sex ratio in last two decade.

According to 2001 census the maximum sex ratio is recorded in Khanapur taluk (989), while, minimum sex ratio is recorded in Athani taluk (949). Similarly there are wide disparities from Rural to Urban sex ratio. The rural sex ratio in 2001 it is recorded maximum in Khanapur taluk (995) and minimum in Raibag taluk (946). The urban sex ratio in 2001 it is recorded highest in Ramdurg taluk (981) and minimum in Raibag taluk (923).

Table 2 Sex Ratios in Rural and Urban Taluks of Belagavi District, 2001 and 2011

SL no	Taluk	Sex Ratio 2001			Sex Ratio 2011		
		Total	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban
1	Athani	949	948	967	958	955	990
2	Bailhongal	969	975	977	981	977	1005
3	Belgavi	946	969	936	967	968	967
4	Chikkodi	950	946	972	966	959	998
5	Gokak	972	975	966	990	988	996
6	Hukkeri	967	970	951	991	991	992
7	Khanapur	989	995	959	976	975	983
8	Raibag	943	946	923	958	957	961
9	Ramdurg	971	971	981	975	970	1006
10	Savadatti	967	967	968	974	971	1002
Belagavi district total		960	964	950	973	970	979

Source: calculated by using data taken from the Census of India 2001 and provisional Population Tables 2011

Chart 2 Disparity in Rural and Urban sex ratio of Belagavi District 2001-2011

Source: calculated by using data taken from the Census of India 2001 and provisional Population Tables 2011

According to 2011 census the maximum sex ratio is recorded in Hukkeri taluk (991), while, minimum sex ratio is recorded in Athanitaluk (958). The rural sex ratio in 2011 it is recorded maximum in Hukkerirtaluk (991) and minimum in Athanitaluk (955). The urban sex ratio in 2011 it is recorded highest in Ramdurgtaluk (1006) and minimum in Raibagtaluk (961).

The urban sex ratio shows positive change in Bailhongal(1005), Ramdurg (1006) and Savadatti(1002). The positive improvement in sex ratio is actually an indication of a decrease in female foeticide in urban taluks.

VII. GENDER DISPARITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

With regard to educational indicators in primary, secondary and tertiary level rural India is lagging behind urban India. The Right to Education Act (RTE) passed in August 2009 has committed the Government of India to the provision of free and compulsory education to all Indian children (Das & Pathak, 2012).

Table 3: Net attendance rate- Lower primary School and Higher primary School 2012-13

SL no	Name of the taluk	Lower primary School			Higher primary School		
		Boys % of attendance	Girls % of attendance	Total % of attendance	Boys % of attendance	Girls % of attendance	Total % of attendance
1.	Athani	93.33	99.17	76.25	93.53	99.21	96.38
2.	Bailhongal	97.03	97.46	97.00	97.33	97.44	97.00
3.	Belgavi	97.68	98.11	97.00	98.15	97.74	96.00
4.	Chikkodi	99.79	99.12	99.45	99.96	99.81	98.88
5.	Gokak	96.46	96.51	96.48	95.63	74.01	84.82
6.	Hukkeri	99.00	99.28	96.14	99.02	99.67	99.34
7.	Khanapur	97.82	98.54	97.00	97.04	97.85	97.00
8.	Raibag	89.84	88.63	89.23	98.74	100.00	99.34
9.	Ramdurg	98.10	98.47	98.00	97.65	97.82	97.00
10.	Savadatti	97.56	97.62	97.00	97.33	97.14	97.00
Belgavi district total		77.10	77.68	74.86	77.94	76.57	76.88

Data source: calculated by using data taken from the Belgaum district at glance 2012-13

Chart 3: Net attendance rate- Lower primary School 2012-13

Source: calculated by using data taken from the Belgaum district at glance 2012-13

Chart 4: Net attendance rate- Higher primary School 2012-13

Source: Calculated by using data taken from the Belgaum district at glance 2012-13

Attendance of students mainly in primary schools is very important for acquiring knowledge and learning skills. The attendance has significantly improved after the Mid-Day meal programmes introduced by government of Karnataka (Secretaries & Delhi, n.d.). Table no 3 shows that the primary school net attendance ratios for the 2012 and 2013 school years. Belagavi districts net attendance rate in lower primary schools is 74.86% while Boys attendance ratio is 77.10 % and Girls attendance ratio is 77.68%. Attendance of girls is more than boy's attendance ratio. The net attendance rate in higher primary schools is 76.88% while Boys attendance ratio is 77.94% and Girls attendance ratio is 76.57%. Attendance of girls is less than boy's attendance ratio. The girl's attendance of lower primary school is low in Raibag taluk; interestingly Raibag taluk achieves 100% attendance in higher primary school during 2012 and 2013. Similarly the girl's attendance of higher primary school is low in Gokak taluk (74.01%) and high in Raibag taluk (100%). Some studies cited the reasons for the low attendance rate are familial commitment, migration, climate induced disasters, famine and poverty led the girl children to abandon schools.

CONCLUSION

The spatial variation of literacy in Belagavi district shows a wide gap of 17.62% literacy from male to female. The minimum male literacy is in Raibag taluk 75.53% and maximum in Belgavi taluk 89.63%. There was observed that the minimum female literacy was 54.94% in Ramdurg taluk to a maximum of 77.54% in Belgavi taluk. It shows that there are wide disparities from the male-female literacy rates. It is, however, encouraging to note that sex disparity in literacy in the district has been gradually decreasing

during the last decades. This is the indicative of increasing spread of female education in different taluks of Belagavi district. Further studies of disparity in literacy and sex ratio are under progress in our research work.

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